

Tracer Study of Adsorption Isotherms. Part III : Ca^{++} and Sr^{++} Ions on Aluminium and Br^- and I^- Ions on Glass

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The adsorption kinetics of labelled calcium and strontium ions on aluminium and halide ions on glass from the aqueous solutions of their salts with varying concentrations in the range 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} M at 30° has been investigated. The steady state values of adsorption at various concentrations agree well with the Freundlich isotherm in all the systems. The growth rate of calcium and strontium uptake follows the direct logarithmic rate equation. It is noted that the strontium adsorption is stronger than that of calcium. The adsorption of iodide and bromide ions on glass follows first order kinetics over the concentration range studied. The order observed for the adsorption on glass at steady state is $\text{Cl}^- \ll \text{Br}^- < \text{I}^-$; the relative adsorptions being in agreement with the corresponding oxidation potentials of these ions.

The applications of radioactive isotopes proved to be very efficient and useful in understanding the mechanism of the different adsorption processes specially at very low concentrations. Studies of adsorption of tracer Pb^{++} and Bi^{++} ions on glass showed that the deposition of these ions is partially due to ion exchange¹. Langer^{2,3} studied the mechanism of such an exchange in the case of silver ions and silver salts in aqueous solution. Palacios and Baptista⁴ demonstrated that the adsorption of $^{65}\text{Zn}^{++}$ on the surfaces of various metals (Pb, Ag, Au, Pt, Ni, Fe and Pd) is followed by cation exchange. Adsorption reactions^{5,6} at glass and metal surfaces have been studied using the radioisotopes ^{24}Na , ^{134}Cs , ^{110}Ag , ^{14}C and ^{82}Br . The effect of time of immersion, the pH of the solution and the pretreatment of the surface were found to affect the rate of adsorption. Arnikar and Mehta^{7,8} studied the adsorption isotherms of iodide ions on metals at micro and tracer concentrations. A logarithmic plot of the saturation amount adsorbed and the equilibrium concentration of the solute showed that the isotherms for I^- -Au and I^- -Pt systems follow the Langmuir equation at low concentrations and the Freundlich equation at higher concentrations ($> 10^{-7}\text{M}$) whereas the isotherm for I^- -Ni system follows Langmuir expression at all the concentrations studied.

We now present results of our study of adsorption isotherms of Ca^{++} and Sr^{++} ions on aluminium and halide ions on glass.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental set up, surface treatment and the preparation of the adsorbent coupons of aluminium and of glass (microscopic cover glasses of Matsunami, Japan), the labelling of the adsorbate system, the radioactive measurements and the calculation of number of layers adsorbed were described earlier^{7,8}. The adsorbate systems consisted of 75 ml of

10^{-1} to 10^{-5} M solutions of $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ tagged with ^{90}Sr and ^{45}Ca respectively for adsorption on aluminium. The halide solutions used for studying adsorption on glass consisted of 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} M solutions of (i) NaI (^{131}I) and (ii) NaBr (^{82}Br). All the adsorbate solutions were at $\text{pH} = 7$ and maintained at 30° . Separate adsorbent coupons were used for each period of adsorption. The activity on the coupons corresponding to each period of adsorption extending from 1 min to 200 hr was measured using an end-window G.M. counter.

$\log a$ (a being the number of layers adsorbed at steady state of adsorption) versus $\log c$ (c being the initial concentration of the adsorbate) was plotted and the values of constants K and n of the Freundlich equation were calculated. The growth rate of adsorption of Ca^{++} and Sr^{++} ions on aluminium was found to fit into the Elovich equation and from the plot of a_t (the number of layers adsorbed at time t) versus $\log t$, the constants of the Elovich equation, p and K' were calculated. In the case of halide ion adsorption on glass, the adsorption rate followed first order kinetics, the corresponding rate constant (k) was calculated from the plot of $\log(1-F)$ versus t (F being the fraction a_t/a).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(A) *Adsorption of Ca^{++} and Sr^{++} ions on aluminium*: The adsorption-rate isotherms for Ca^{++} and Sr^{++} ions on aluminium are similar in nature. The adsorption at steady state decreases with the fall in concentration of the adsorbate. Both the curves are continuous and concave towards time axis tending to saturation, *vide* Fig. 1. In the case of adsorption of Sr^{++} ions, the adsorption rate as well as the steady state values vary but slightly over the

Fig. 1. Rates of adsorption of Ca^{++} ions on aluminium at different concentrations.

concentration range 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} M . There is, however, a very sudden fall in these values at concentrations below 10^{-4} M . These results fit well with the Freundlich isotherm, $a = Kc^{1/n}$, where K and n are constants. The rate of adsorption of Sr^{++} ions is found to be greater than that of Ca^{++} ions over the entire range of concentrations studied. The number of layers adsorbed at steady state, a , is obtained in each case from the growth-rate curves,

the variation of $\log a$ with $\log c$ being linear (Fig. 2). In both the cases of adsorption the Freundlich constant, n , is greater than unity which is consistent with the fact that the adsorption tends to a saturation limit. It may be seen from Table I that n is nearly the same for Ca^{++} and Sr^{++} ions, while the K values differ appreciably. The higher K value of Sr^{++} -Al system corresponds to the faster uptake of Sr^{++} ions on aluminium as compared to that of Ca^{++} ions in the Ca^{++} -Al system. At the steady state the free cations are in equilibrium with those already deposited on the aluminium metal, and the process stands out as a limiting case of polar adsorption⁹. In the Sr^{++} -Al system this equilibrium is more on the adsorption-product side. The Hofmeister's lyotropic series of flocculation values of

Fig. 2. Freundlich adsorption isotherms of Sr^{++} and Ca^{++} ions on aluminium and of I^- and Br^- ions on glass.

negatively charged colloidal particles, including those of metals, holds good for the adsorbability of various ions⁹ and according to this Sr^{++} ions get adsorbed more strongly than Ca^{++} ions.

The results on the kinetics of adsorption of Sr^{++} and Ca^{++} ions on aluminium fit into the Elovich equation¹⁰ which is expressed more commonly in the integrated form as

$$a_t = 2.303 (\log pK' + \log t)/p$$

where a_t is the amount reacted (number of layers adsorbed) in time t , and p and K' are constants. The equation, also known as the direct logarithmic rate equation, has been found to be valid over almost all known cases of chemisorption in gas-metal systems at relatively

TABLE 1

Values of the Freundlich adsorption constants n and K computed from adsorption isotherm ($\log a$ versus $\log c$).

System	n	K (number of layers adsorbed at unit concentration)
Sr^{++} —Al	2.09	50.00
Ca^{++} —Al	2.21	5.50
I^- —Glass	3.19	1.74
Br^- —Glass	2.39	1.32

low temperatures¹¹. Linear plots¹² of a versus $\log t$ (Figs. 3 and 4) lead to the values of the constants p and K' . It is observed that K' , the number of layers, representing the initial velocity of the reaction, increases with the increase in the initial concentration of the solution.

Fig. 3. Elovich plots for the adsorption of Ca^{++} ions on aluminium at different concentrations.

In gas-metal systems such a variation in K' with pressure is anticipated in theory and has been observed in practice¹³. The factor $(1/pK')$, normally written as t_0 , having the dimensions of time, is nearly constant for different concentrations (see Table 2). The new

constant, t_0 , being greater than zero, signifies slow uptake¹⁴ of the cations. It is the basic requirement of the Elovich kinetics that the rate determining process is the production of a chemisorbed ion, in which electrons have to arrive at the edge of the barrier from the metal and then cross over to the adsorbed phase. As the adsorption proceeds the height of the

Fig. 4. Elovich plots for the adsorption of Sr⁺⁺ ions on aluminium at different concentrations.

barrier increases and the electron transfer leading to further adsorption becomes increasingly difficult; hence the process slows down. As revealed by our experiments no desorption nor measurable surface diffusion of the metallic ions occurred on aluminium even at 500° proving that these ions are chemisorbed at the aluminium surface.

TABLE 2

Values of the Elovich adsorption constants K' and p computed from adsorption isotherm (a_t versus $\log t$)

System	Conc. M	K' (layers hr ⁻¹)	p (layer ⁻¹)	$t_0 = 1/pK'$ (hr)
Sr ⁺⁺ —Al	10 ⁻¹	31.0	0.057	0.566
	10 ⁻²	31.0	0.057	0.566
	10 ⁻³	30.1	0.057	0.583
	10 ⁻⁴	3.5	0.461	0.613
	10 ⁻⁵	0.4	3.53	0.765
Ca ⁺⁺ —Al	10 ⁻¹	0.29	3.57	0.965
	10 ⁻²	0.2	6.25	0.819
	10 ⁻³	0.02	57.57	0.827
	10 ⁻⁴	0.02	57.57	0.827
	10 ⁻⁵	0.01	97.88	0.822

(B) *Adsorption of halide ions on glass* : It is possible that trace amounts of free halogen are formed in such dilute solutions of the adsorbate by oxidation due to the dissolved oxygen. A part of the adsorbed layer on glass may thus consist of the free halogen. Urbanic and Damerell¹⁶ report adsorption of iodine on glass. As pointed out by us earlier¹⁷ the amount of the free halogen thus formed, however, is undetectably small under conditions of present study. The bulk of the adsorbate hence appears to remain in the ionic form.

It is found that the extent of adsorption of I^- and Br^- ions on glass is slight, being less than needed for a monolayer. The adsorption of I^- ions on glass is relatively more than that of Br^- ions. Adsorption of Br^- ions showed an induction period of about 12 hr at low concentrations during which no adsorption occurred. It was further observed that there is no measurable adsorption of Cl^- ions on glass at any concentration. The order observed for adsorption on glass at steady state is $Cl^- \ll Br^- < I^-$. These relative adsorptions are in agreement with the oxidation potentials ($Pt/X_2/X^-$) of these ions ($-0.536 V$ for $X = I$; $-1.07 V$ for $X = Br$ and $-1.36 V$ for $X = Cl$). This is mentioned here only to convey an idea about the relative tendencies of the halide ions to oxidize at an inert surface like glass. This order of the tendencies appears to be same as on a platinum surface, though there is no explanation for this. Hence not much significance can be probably attached to this order.

TABLE 3

First order rate constants for the adsorption of I^- and Br^- ions on glass

System	Conc. M	$k(\text{min}^{-1}) \times 10^3$
I^- —Glass	10^{-1}	1.8
	10^{-2}	1.1
	10^{-3}	1.8
	10^{-4}	1.1
	10^{-5}	1.1
Br^- —Glass	10^{-1}	1.5
	$10^{-2}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-4}$	1.0
	10^{-5}	—

Adsorption of I^- and Br^- on glass obeys the first order rate law. From the plot of $\log(1-F)$ versus time the values of the rate constants (k) are calculated. It is observed that (i) (k) differs only slightly as the concentration varies and (ii) (k_{I^-}) $>$ (k_{Br^-}).

The adsorption of iodine on glass from an iodide solution is explained on the following mechanism. Glass consists essentially of an unending silica network with a terminal structure wherein Na^+ ions are associated to the silica network. While the silica network remains unaffected by water, the terminal structure undergoes slow degradation. Literature on the properties of glass¹⁵ mention the following reaction with the terminal structure when in contact with water

Thus there is ample evidence for the presence of terminal OH in the end structure of glass when in contact with water. The classical work of Weyl¹⁸ shows that when glass is in contact with a dilute acidified solution of NaF the OH group of end structure gets replaced by fluorine as follows :

On the basis of the above reaction we postulate the adsorption of iodine on glass from a solution of NaI :

As in the case of cationic adsorption on aluminium, the adsorption of the halide ions on glass tends to reach a constant maximum, as indicated by the value of the Freundlich constant n being greater than unity. For the other constant K , the number of layers adsorbed at unit concentration, $K_{\text{I}^-} > K_{\text{Br}^-}$. This is in accordance with the observed fact that the I^- adsorption is faster than Br^- adsorption.

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